

UNDERSTANDING THE NEXUS BETWEEN COVID-19 AND CURRENT GLOBAL INFLATION: NIGERIA'S EXPERIENCE AS A CASE STUDY

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Abstract

The inflation rate worldwide is on a galloping trend as prices for goods skyrocketed globally. In May 2024, China had the lowest global inflation rate at 0.10%, while Argentina had the highest rate at 276%. The current global inflation cannot be simply attributed to another world business cycle. It is one of the negative impacts of COVID-19. Since the outbreak of Covid-19, a new work culture has evolved – 'Work from Home', or 'Remote Work'. This study employed a qualitative method of analysis to assess the effect of the coronavirus pandemic on the world economy. It used the Transformationalist's perspective on globalization as a theoretical underpinning. The study notes the nexus which exists among economies of different countries, the volatility of global oil prices in a country like Nigeria, and imported inflation. Essentially, the researcher opined that there is a need for a more cursory examination of the factors contributing to rising global inflation, beyond the conventional classical and neo-classical global economies prognosis. The major view of this study is that the shifting work culture in terms of remote work and supply chain disruptions may be a major contribution to the inflationary pressure being experienced worldwide. This understanding is very didactic if policymakers are to be able to develop more effective policies suitable for addressing rising global prices, while promoting economic stability, sustainable growth and development. Particularly, the Nigeria State was employed as a case study in explaining the present global inflation challenge. The paper recommended among others that there is the need for planned intervention, through thoughtful long-term planning on the part of policymakers beyond the surface-dressing programmes of the Nigerian government and policymakers. In particular, it calls for policy initiatives that will attract investment from both the private and public sectors in the real sector of the economy like the agricultural and industrial sectors.

Keywords: Inflation, Covid-19, Business Cycles, Globalization, Remote Work.

Introduction

The coronavirus pandemic has come and gone, but its adverse consequences are still with us today. One major consequence of it is the rising prices of goods and services globally. Nearly all countries of the world are experiencing increasing prices for goods and services. In May 2024, global statistics on inflation are at an all-time high in almost all countries under consideration. China has the lowest inflationary rate at 0.10%. In the United States, it is 3.27%. Argentina recorded the

highest inflation rate at 276%, while Australia, 3.6% and Canada 2.9% have theirs as 3.6% and 2.9 respectively.

In France, the inflationary rate is slightly above two per cent, unlike Turkey which is as high as 75.45%. The average inflation rate in Nigeria is 27.04 per cent, but food prices inflation is nearly 40% as of August 2024. Zimbabwe has the highest inflation pressure in 2023 with over one hundred and seventy-two per cent inflationary rate to be followed by Sierra Leone at 35.84%, and 32.7% in Malawi as of May 2024. Other inflation rates across Africa as of May 2024 include 23.3% in Ethiopia, Burundi: 12.1%, Gambia: 11.04%, Angola: 30.16%, Ghana: 23.1%, and Guinea: 5.3% as of April 2024. Only China and Italy seem to have low inflation in all the countries mentioned above as nearly every country in the world is experiencing inflation at an increasing rate. (Chinedu Okafor, 2024, Trading Economics, 2024).

One can safely say based on the statistics above that inflation is a global endemic economic problem with far-reaching implications for the citizens of both the third-world countries and the countries in the global north. Simply put, inflation is a situation in which more money is chasing fewer goods due to the large volume of money in circulation. This arises when goods supply is lower than the demand for goods. Central to the present worldwide inflation is diminishing global productivity due to the COVID-19 pandemic. Besides the fact many workforce in different countries died of Coronavirus resulting in fewer hands to work, another thing is the advent of remote work. Remote work is becoming an in-thing and an acceptable worldwide norm. It is important to note that the world now has fewer workers to work in the real sector of the economy, while the service sector is growing at nanoseconds.

The COVID-19 pandemic has brought about unprecedented changes to the way people work and the relationship among important organization stakeholders. Remote work has become the new norm for both the workers and many organizations. This changing work orientation has significant implications for global goods production and distribution. With fewer people working in manufacturing and agriculture, the supply of goods has not kept pace with the demand. This imbalance between the supply of goods and demand for goods is a major driver of the present inflation pressure in the countries of the world. This is because inadequate production leads to higher prices for goods and services. This however is not to relegate the potential contribution of other inflationary factors. (Ogunbukola, Matthew (2024)

Nigeria provides a pertinent case study of this phenomenon. In recent years, there has been a noticeable trend among Nigerian youths gravitating towards service-oriented jobs such as social media content creation, virtual assistance, and tech roles. This change has come at the expense of traditional artisan jobs and direct involvement in agriculture. Today, the Nigerian State faces an acute shortage of manpower as far as artisanship is concerned, due to the unwillingness of the youths to learn and serve in apprenticeship. The old hands are ageing and losing strength and vitality, they cannot work as hard as before; many have even passed away. To worsen this case are the rising insecurities and the adverse effects of climate change on agricultural produce in particular. Consequently, food prices have reached unprecedented highs, especially concerning agricultural products and other household goods. The fact that the Nigeria agricultural sector is largely subsistence and rudimentary has aggravated these issues. Otherwise, mechanized farming and the automation of the country's agricultural processes and operations could have alleviated the

impact of a declining agricultural workforce and helped stabilize food productivity. Unfortunately, this is not the case, hence, the country faces a severe mismatch between food supply and demand which has driven inflation to new heights in recent times. It is also crucial to note that dwindling agricultural produce has also resulted in a scarcity of raw materials for the manufacturing and industrial sectors of the economy.

The COVID-19 pandemic has not only exposed the world to poor health infrastructures and the unpreparedness of nation-states for a pandemic of worldwide proportion. It has also revealed the volatility of world economies and their interconnectedness. Indeed, Covid-19 has shown that the destinies of countries of the world are intertwined, and it may not be out of place to agree with the International Labour Organization that -

Poverty anywhere constitutes a danger to prosperity everywhere, the war against want requires to be carried on with unrelenting vigour with each nation, and by continuous and concerted international effort. *This is because one nation's problem is another nation's headache.* (ILO's 1944 Declaration of Philadelphia, emphasis mine).

The world at present faces inflation of monumental proportions. Prices of consumables and non-consumable goods are on the increase, the standard of living is on a viral decline due to lower purchasing power. It therefore becomes imperative to understand the factors contributing to the present global inflation. Besides the conventional causes of inflation commonly categorized as demand-pull inflation, cost-push inflation, devaluation, and rising wages, among others, the impact of the shifting workforce dynamics is the major focus of this study. (Benjamin Curry & Kat Tretina, 2022).

It is the modest view of this researcher that policymakers need to develop more effective initiatives, strategies, and policies to stabilize economies and promote sustainable growth, taking into consideration the changing work orientation. This study denounced the tendencies of Nigeria's leaders' recurring habit of throwing money at problems without addressing the underlying issues, which often exacerbates such problems. During the Buhari regime, for instance, several initiatives like the Anchor Borrowers Program and Trader Moni yielded minimal results, despite billions of naira expended on these schemes. While these projects intended to boost agriculture and small businesses, respectively, the lack of tangible outcomes underscores the inefficiency of simply injecting funds without efficient planning and implementation. Nigeria today faces two major economic issues: food scarcity and inflation. Addressing these challenges could alleviate other problems, such as insecurity and unemployment. The pressing question is: how do we achieve this? Attempts to answer this question may require our understanding of inflation as a concept and a historical analysis of Nigeria's inflationary pressure. (Abdulkareem Mojeed, 2023, Shidali Nasiru (2022).

Research Methodology

The methodology employed in this study is primarily qualitative and historical, while the Transformationalists theory of globalization serves as the study's theoretical underpinning. It is qualitative in that it relies on self-observation and past academic works by others, such as scholarly articles, periodicals, online publications, and related literature. It is historical in that it traces Nigeria's inflationary trend from independence to date to discern a common pattern(s).

REMOTE WORK AND GLOBALIZATION - THE IMPLICATION FOR THE NATIONAL AND GLOBAL INFLATION EXPLAINED

Today, globalization has become a highly relatable concept, permeating everything from commerce to politics, technology to tourism, economy to environment, and social media to science. Nearly every individual on Earth engages in daily interactions with individuals beyond their local spheres of influence. However, as with all social phenomena, it carries both positive and negative implications.

The theory of globalization has several perspectives. The world-system theory views the world as consisting of core, peripheral, and semi-peripheral countries. The Core Countries are nation-states like the USA, Canada, and Britain, among others, with strong democratic institutions and well-industrialized and developed economies. Less developed countries such as Nigeria, Ghana, Afghanistan, and Cuba form the periphery, heavily relying on Western countries for their survival. Semi-periphery countries oscillate between the central and peripheral countries. There is also the modernization theory, which emphasizes the tendency for less developed countries to gravitate towards imbibing Western values and cultures as a result of globalization. According to the dependency theory of globalization, developed countries are seen as usurpers and exploiters of periphery countries rather than partners in growth and development. Proponents of this theory argue that the core countries have consistently found ways to make the peripheral countries subservient through colonialism and neo-colonialism. The hyper-globalist viewpoint views globalization as ushering in a new era of global integration, where national economies and cultures are blending into a unified global system. In this view, nation-states are diminishing in significance as the world evolves into a single global society. The skeptical perspective, on the other hand, questions the notion that globalization is unprecedented. It argues that the current level of economic integration is comparable to previous periods, such as the late 19th century. Sceptics maintain that national borders remain crucial and that globalization is more of a regional phenomenon than a truly global one. (Khan Academy, 2014).

In this study, we focus on the Transformationalist's perspective on globalization. Globalization, according to Transformationalists, is a complex network of interconnected relationships that largely exercises power in indirect ways. They assert that cultural exchange is a reciprocal interaction, where cultures from the developing world influence, alter and enrich Western culture, rather than a one-way process from the West to the developing world. Transformationalists also believe that globalization can be managed or reversed, especially by addressing its negative effects. In actuality, globalization is never a one-sided phenomenon. There is constant cultural interaction between these two relationships. Numerous firsthand reports have confirmed that Afro-music is well-accepted in North American and European nations. An examination of social media indicates a rise in interracial unions. African cuisine and clothing are becoming popular at parties in the West, in addition to international music. (Karl Thompson, 2018).

According to the Financial Times,

In recent years it (Afrobeats) has crossed over to the mainstream, its biggest stars filling stadiums and infiltrating airwaves across Europe and the US. Its global popularity has been marked by

Grammy wins, viral dance videos and sold-out arena tours. In July, Afrobeats superstar Wizkid will play London's 62,000-seat Tottenham Hotspur Stadium... Afrobeats has been embraced by some of the world's biggest pop stars. Beyoncé leaned on many of the scene's leading protagonists for her Grammy-nominated soundtrack album *The Lion King: The Gift* and there have been hit remix collaborations between Justin Bieber and Wizkid (on the singalong anthem "Essence") and Selena Gomez and Benin City boy Rema on "Calm Down". Most recently, at February's NBA All-Star Game in Utah, newly crowned Grammy winner Tems, Rema and the more established Burna Boy performed a medley of their hits. A fresh generation of fans with similar heritages to these stars sang along in English and Pidgin English. (Christian Adofo, 2023 – emphasis mine)

Remote work is one of the latest harbingers of globalization. It is revolutionizing the service industry. Indeed, until recently, globalization primarily focused on the trade of goods rather than services. Companies' ability to hire remote workers enables—for the first time—global service trade. This will have major implications for the global economy. (Kleanthis Georgaris, 2024—emphasis mine). On the positive side, remote work can help to reduce brain drain (human capital flight) especially from the developing countries to developed countries, bring about competition and higher wages for local talents in the developing countries, democratize opportunity for both talents and clients, provide cheap labour for industries in the developed world, and assist developing countries boost their income generation through (direct and indirect) taxes paid by citizens working remotely. Conversely, remote work can also present challenges, particularly when it comes to collaborative and creative tasks. Such tasks often require face-to-face interaction and brainstorming, which can be difficult to achieve remotely. Furthermore, remote work can lead to feelings of isolation and lack of motivation, which can negatively impact productivity. (Kleanthis Georgaris (2024) and Ogunbukola (2024)).

UNDERSTANDING THE NIGERIA INFLATIONARY PRESSURE – A HISTORICAL PERSPECTIVE

Nigeria officially became a federating and independent state on October 1, 1960. The aforementioned events, including the annexation of Lagos as a Crown Colony in 1861, the unification of the Southern Protectorate in 1898, the unification of the Northern Protectorate in 1900, the naming of the country as Nigeria in 1898, and the unification of the Southern and Northern Protectorates in 1914 by Sir Fedrick Lugard, the Governor General of Nigeria, are important historical events culminating in the emergence of the Nigeria State. Equally crucial, are the various constitutional evolutions, from the Clifford Constitution of 1922 to the Lyttleton Constitution of 1954, and the numerous Constitutional Conferences held in Lagos and London, among other places.

The inflation rate in Nigeria was 5.44% in 1960, -3.73% in 1967, and -0.48% in 1968, coinciding with the partial period of Nigeria's Civil War. It rose in 1969 to 10.16, 13.76% in 1970, and 16% in 1971. In 1972, it was 3.46%, and 5.40% in 1973. The inflation rate in Nigeria rose to 12.67% in 1974 and 33.96% in 1975. It was 24.30 in 1976, 15.09% in 1977, and 21.71% in 1978. It dropped to 11.71% in 1979, 9.97% in 1980, and sporadically rose to 20.81% in 1981. Starting from 1982 to 1989, the inflation rate in Nigeria was 7.70%, 23.21%, 17.82%, 7.44%, 5.72%, 11.29%, and 54.47% in the consecutive years. It dropped to 7.36% in 1990 and slightly rose to 13.01% in 1991. Between 1992 and 1995, Nigeria's inflation rate oscillated between 44.59% and 72.84%, with the latter being Nigeria's all-time highest inflationary rate to date. (National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), Mary Izuaka, Channels TV, and World Data Info).

The inflation rate in Nigeria dropped to 29.27% in 1996, 8.53% in 1997, rose to 10.00% in 1998, dropped back to 6.62% in 1999 (Nigeria election year), and 6.93% in 2000. It again rose to 18.87% in 2001, slightly dropped to 12.88% in 2002, and rose back to 14.03% in 2003, 15.00% in 2004, and 17.86% in 2005. In 2006, it went down to 8.23%, and in 2007 (Nigeria election year), it went down to 5.39%. It was 11.58% in 2008, 12.55% in 2009, and 13.72% in 2010. It became 10.84% in 2011 (the Nigerian election year) and 12.22% in 2012. It revolved between 8.48% and 9.01% from 2013 to 2015 (the Nigerian election year) before rising to 15.70% in 2016. It was 16.50% in 2016, 12.10% in 2017, 13.25% in 2018, 11.440% in 2019, 13.25% in 2020, 16.95% in 2021, and 18.85% in 2022. (World Data Info, 2024, Verivafrika, 2024).

One quick common observation from the above data is that the Nigerian inflation rate mostly comes down during election year and goes up the next year after every change of government or election year since the dawn of the fourth republic. Nigeria's inflation rate was 6.62% in 1999 (Nigeria election year) and 6.93% in 2000; 14.03% in 2003 to 15.00% in 2004, 10.84% in 2011 (Nigeria election year); and 12.22% in 2012, 9.01% (Nigeria election year) to 16.50% in 2016, 11.440% in 2019 to 13.25% in 2020. Nigeria's annual inflation rate rose to 28.92 per cent in December 2023, from 28.20 per cent in November to 33.69% in April 2024. Perhaps this is because a significant amount of money is released for elections and electioneering campaigns at every election in the country. (National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), 2023, 2024; Mary Izuaka, 2024; Channels TV, 2024; World Data Info, 2024.)

This study also notes and observes in agreement with Sani Bawa et al (2020) that:

... oil price increases led to an increase in headline, core and food measures of inflation in Nigeria. However, a decline in oil price resulted in a decline in the marginal cost of production and culminated in moderation of domestic inflation. Furthermore, negative oil price shocks led to higher inflation in Nigeria when exchange rate is dropped from the models, indicating that exchange rate absorbed the impact of oil price declines earlier, as lower oil prices culminated in lower external reserve, depreciation of the naira and ultimately higher inflationary pressures. Also, core inflation tends to respond more to oil price increases than food inflation. These results were robust to changes in econometric specifications and sample period. We can also draw further conclusions about the inflationary trends in Nigeria from 1960 to 2024, specifically the economic, political, and social factors that shaped these changes. From 1960 to 1969, appropriating the Nigerian early independence and Civil War years, inflation remained relatively low, with some deflation during the Civil War (1967-1970). This period reflects economic instability and disruption caused by the war. Inflation rates spiked to double digits in 1969, principally due to the post-war recovery effort. The 1970-1980 period represents a period of oil boom and volatility, such that the inflation rate remained high in the early 1970s, peaking at 33.96% in 1975. This was an oil boom, which brought in significant revenue but also increased inflationary pressures. The inflation rate dropped, but remained volatile in the late 1970s. Stabilization policies and fluctuating oil prices may have contributed to the decline in the late 1970s. One major policy worth mentioning is the Nigerian Third National Development Plan of 1975 to 1980. (Nwosu, H. N. (1977)

Following this period is the economic turmoil and structural adjustments program from 1980 to 1990. In the early 1980s, inflation rates fluctuated significantly. The early 1980s saw high inflation, likely due to global economic recession and internal mismanagement. The introduction of the Structural Adjustment Program (SAP) in 1986 further compounded this, leading to high inflation that peaked at 54.47% in 1989 due to currency devaluation and the removal of subsidies. The Nigerian state experienced a series of political instability and economic reforms from 1990-2000. Political instability and high inflation marked the years 1990–1995, with rates reaching

72.84% in 1995, the highest ever recorded. Political instability and economic mismanagement influenced this. Inflation decreased significantly from 1996 to 2000, with rates dropping to single digits in a few years. This period includes the transition to civilian rule in 1999.

From 2000 to 2010, the advent of civilian rule led to several economic reforms, resulting in significant economic growth, a low debt profile, poverty reduction, and lower inflation. Although there were some fluctuations from 2000 to 2007, the overall trend was downward. The period saw economic reforms and relative political stability. The short-lived success and gains from 2008 to 2010 were due to the global financial crisis, which contributed to higher inflation during these years. Generally, the inflation rate remained in single digits from 2011 to 2015, mostly low during election years, reflecting potential government efforts to stabilize the economy or manipulate it. However, inflation began to rise after 2015, reaching a peak of 18.85% in 2022. Factors could include recession, COVID-19 pandemic effects, and global economic trends. Current data indicates continued high inflation, influenced by ongoing national and global economic challenges.

Key Deductions

Political Instability: Periods of political instability, such as during the Civil War and military rule, correspond to higher inflation rates.

Economic Policies: Structural adjustments and economic reforms have had mixed impacts, sometimes stabilizing the economy but also causing short-term inflation spikes.

Global Influences: Global economic conditions, including fluctuations in oil prices, financial crises, and most recently, COVID-19, also impact Nigeria's inflation.

Election Cycles: Inflation trends suggest potential manipulation or stabilization efforts during election years to maintain economic stability. These insights explain the complex interplay of domestic policies, political events, and global economic conditions on Nigeria's inflation trends over the decades.

This research further observed that inflation has been on the rise in Nigeria since 2020, when the coronavirus became a worldwide pandemic, and has been on an unabated rising trajectory. Other African countries such as Ghana, South Africa, and Egypt, among others, also exhibit similar trends. Egypt's inflation rate was 5.04% in 2020, 5.21% in 2021, and 13.90% in 2022, but declined to 2.2% in January 2024. (Macrotrends, 2024). Food inflation is currently very high, peaking at over 40% in May 2024. The cost of family-size bread is nearly \$2000. The government therefore needs to make important interventions to change this narrative.

TACKLING FOOD SCARCITY AND INFLATION IN NIGERIA— RECOMMENDATIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

To tackle food scarcity, the government needs to embark on a comprehensive mechanized farming initiative. The Federal Government, through the Ministry of Agriculture, should invest in thousands of tractors and establish large-scale farmlands across the six geopolitical zones. Recruiting willing and able individuals to work on these farms incentivized by favourable

remuneration can significantly boost agricultural productivity. Moreover, sourcing high-yield crop seeds, both locally and internationally, to cultivate staples like cassava, maize, rice, millet, and soybeans can ensure a steady supply of essential food items. Establishing value chain firms to process farm products will enhance the agricultural sector's efficiency and output. Encouraging private individuals to invest in the agricultural drive by providing implements rather than money can foster a more hands-on and sustainable approach to farming. If the government implements these measures, Nigeria could overcome food insufficiency within a few months. This would lead to increased GDP, reduced unemployment rates, and, consequently, lower inflation.

The COVID-19 pandemic has emphasized the interdependence of the global economy and brought to light vulnerabilities that require attention. By understanding the factors contributing to global inflation, such as the shifting workforce dynamics and supply chain disruptions, policymakers can develop more effective strategies to stabilize economies and promote sustainable growth. Nigeria's experience serves as a microcosm of the larger global inflation challenge. The need for strategic intervention focused on addressing root causes rather than symptomatic relief is critical. Only through thoughtful, long-term planning and investment can Nigeria and other nations navigate the complexities of global inflation and achieve economic stability.

CONCLUSION

During this study, we discovered that current inflation is a worldwide phenomenon affecting both countries in the southern and northern hemispheres. The paper has also noted COVID-19's significant impact on world economies and its negative effects. It is our view that to address these challenges, a new economic orientation may be necessary. Both developing and developed countries must seek to increase productivity across all sectors of the economy. This might involve investing in mechanization and modern agricultural techniques, encouraging a balanced distribution of the workforce across different sectors, and developing policies that support both traditional and emerging industries.

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